

Earth Action: Sea Level Rise, Coastal Risk, and Resilience

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1. State of the Problem: environmental and socio-economic impacts of sea level rise

As our planet warms, the volume of Earth's ocean continues to increase. Today, the ocean gains about 300 trillion gallons of liquid water every year (e.g., *Vinogradova & Hamlington 2022*). The expanding ocean gradually takes over land, increasing the risk of inundation and flooding of the coastal regions where nearly half of the world population resides, and potentially exposing more than 300 million people to flood risk by 2050 across the globe (e.g., *Kulp and Strauss, 2019*). The impact of rising seas differs geographically. For example, sea level rates along the U.S. eastern seaboard are 3-4 times higher than the global average and continues to accelerate (e.g., *Davis & Vinogradova 2017*), threatening America's trillion-dollar coastal property market and public infrastructure. As a direct consequence of this rise, flooding in the U.S. coastal community has doubled in frequency since 2000 (e.g., *Hamlington, Vinogradova et al., 2021*), posing risk not only to the public infrastructure, but also to the U.S. military installations and energy storage and distribution facilities located on coasts or at major inland ports (e.g., *Vinogradova & Hamlington 2022*). Once in contact with land, rising ocean exacerbates land loss through coastal erosion and land subsidence. Furthermore, additional saltwater can infiltrate and interact with groundwater aquifers as well as mix with the surface water, resulting in the loss of freshwater supplies. For many island nations with the groundwater being the only reliable source of drinking water, the loss of freshwater aquifers from sea level rise produces devastating effect, which is often further exacerbated by droughts due to inter-annual climate variability, air-sea coupled process like El Niño, and intensified water cycle (e.g., *Vinogradova 2017*).

To address both environmental and socio-economic impacts of rising ocean and help humanity prepare for future consequences of climate change, government agencies, academia, private and public partners continue to develop strategies to measure and predict the impacts of these changes. The success of these collective efforts is rooted in fundamental observations and science, evidence-based knowledge, and timely access to the information that informs resilience and risk mitigation efforts. How does NASA contribute to these national and global efforts?

2. What does NASA do about sea level rise and coastal changes

NASA plays a leading role in providing accurate and trusted information that quantifies and communicates how sea-level related hazards are changing. This information improves our understanding of present day and future threats at the coast, which in turn enables sound public policy and risk-informed decision making. In addition, recognizing the inherent diversity of sea level and coastal stakeholders and associated challenges when transitioning sea-level

science into actionable guidance (e.g., *Hinkel et al., 2019*), NASA established a direct link to boundary organizations through a dedicated Sea Level Practitioner [Board](#) that consists of experts in translating science into actionable information. This board helps collect and communicate needs, and engages in co-development and delivery of tools that are useful to stakeholders.

To ensure the delivery of robust and trusted information, NASA through the work of Sea Level Change Team ([N-SLCT](#)), has adopted a two-pronged approach in working with stakeholders: 1) create foundational sea-level information for a broad base of stakeholders; 2) perform targeted research using NASA observations and models to address specific stakeholder needs. Such approach allows us to address known challenges that are common for the flow of information from a remote-sensing scientist or technologist to an ultimate end-user or consumer of sea-level information (e.g., *Moon et al. 2020; Sobel 2021*). The approach leverages NASA’s well-regarded Agency end-to-end capabilities, spanning technological, scientific and application domains.

3. NASA research-to-action framework and flow of sea level information

NASA’s (e.g., N-SLCT) research-to-action emphasis follows an established flow of information, as summarized in Figure 1 and detailed in the sections below.

Figure 1: Research-to-action and flow of information within NASA sea level enterprise. Asterisks denote future missions. It is worth noting that the direction of the flow is not always unidirectional, with user needs informing (some) basic research.

3.1 Continued monitoring of sea level and coastal changes

Predicting sea level rise and adapting for its consequences begins with measuring the signal. NASA has been a critical partner in the satellite missions measuring global sea level change since they began more than 30 years ago with the NASA-CNES TOPEX/Poseidon radar altimeter mission. NASA’s continued participation in radar altimetry missions has proven extremely successful. Not only has NASA continued to contribute improved key instruments (like the

radiometer), but its participation has also made it possible to improve accuracy requirements to meet the climate monitoring demands. Without NASA's contribution to these missions, observing the acceleration in the rate of rise, and using it as a basis for near term predictions would not be possible. Maintaining NASA's leading role in the sea level enterprise begins with our engineering workforce who ensure production of high-precision technologies needed to observe even slightest variations in sea level over the globe.

3.2 Developing New Knowledge and Integrated Science Products

With the satellite altimeter observations and data from other NASA and partner platforms, we now know how fast and why sea level is changing near coastal cities around the world. The accuracy and longevity of NASA's sea-level observatory have deepened our understanding of the physics of the Earth system. These data have also allowed scientists to improve climate models and physics-based projections of processes and changes in the ocean and atmosphere and on land, including those in the recent IPCC's assessments (*IPCC, 2021*). NASA invests in multiple modeling and data integration systems to leverage global satellite observations and state-of-the-art physical models, including ECCO, GISS Model E, GMAO, EIS (sea level), JPL's SLPS framework, IPCC/FACTS, multiple regional data assimilation and Digital Twin systems.

To produce accurate estimates of present and future state of the Earth's ocean requires more than just hardware or software. International and inter-disciplinary teams of several hundred scientists, engineers and technicians conduct research with these measurements and maintain constant scrutiny of the sea level record (e.g., OSTST, N-SLCT, PO, Coastal Resilience, and multiple members across ESD teams). NASA's leadership in maintaining those teams is what gives us the ability to see not only how fast sea level is rising, but also how quickly that rate of rise is increasing. In addition to ensuring its accuracy, NASA teams exploit altimeter data to better understand regional ocean changes (which directly affect local sea level impacts), improve hurricane prediction and marine weather forecasts (altimeters also provide global measurements of the wind and waves over the oceans). On the whole, these human resources play as large a role in facilitating actionable climate information as the satellites do.

3.3 Translating Recent Discoveries into Actionable Science

Coordinated research-to-action efforts enable the delivery of accessible information related to coastal sea level prediction on synoptic (e.g., storms), seasonal, decadal and centennial planning horizons, as well as assessments of ongoing and future sea-level impacts (e.g., flooding). NASA, e.g., through N-SLCT, adopts a cross-cutting approach to work across the broad user landscape to provide foundational information from which action can be taken and also has the agility to meet specific user needs that arise.

Adoption of this approach has led to multiple stakeholder efforts with partners, including Department of Defense (impact of sea level rise and saltwater intrusion on military installation and national security), UN Rising Nations Initiative (foundational science and impact assessment for Pacific Islands to aid in climate refugees efforts), IPCC (first US government partnership with

the UN IPCC to deliver consensus climate projections), NOAA (improve technical predicting capabilities and delivery of sea level information), the World Bank (improve information for clients, PEERS (data and interpretation to a global community of practitioners engaging in dynamic adaptation planning), and others. NASA continues to engage with multiple stakeholders, co-developing appropriate [climate tools](#) that aid decision-making process and improve climate services.

3.4 Coordinating Service Delivery across Federal and International Partners

NASA is an integral part of the global and Federal sea level enterprise, including WH Sea Level Rise Task Force, WH Climate Task Force, USGCRP, NOPP, WCRP, CLIVAR, UN Decade with N-SLCT selected as its official Programme of the UN Decade, and other efforts. Our strength is the ability to provide timely, accurate, open, and data-driven information about sea level rise and coastal hazards. Given fast-evolving state of the Earth system, providing current information is key to being relevant and useful in sea level enterprise. NASA’s other unique strength in national and global partnerships is a prominent role of NASA scientists that help fill gaps and support user community in a better way, strengthening NASA’s research-to-action emphasis.

Table 1: Summary for the Sea Level Rise and Coastal Resilience Earth Action. Asterisk indicates future missions.

Environmental impacts of sea level rise	Economic & Societal impacts of sea level rise	NASA assets and long-term assumptions for addressing sea level rise problem	Stakeholders, Users	Teams, Workforce
Increased flooding	Coastal infrastructure	Direct satellite observations of global sea level (reference data): Jason-3, S6 MF, B, C	NOAA, FEMA, and other Agencies	NASA Sea Level Change Team (N-SLCT)
Inundation	Real estate, urban planning		States	
Storm surges	Energy storage & distribution facilities	Satellite observations of coastal and polar sea level from SWOT, IS2, CRISTAL*	US Military	NASA Coastal Resilience Team (CR)
Land Erosion	Military installations & national security		WH SOST, OSTP	OSTST
Contamination of groundwater	Marine Commerce & resource management	Satellite observations of sea level components: GFO, MC (ocean mass, land ice), InSAR, NISAR* (land motion), S6, CIMR* (ocean dynamics)	UN	NASA-DoD WG
Loss of freshwater supplies	Public health		WCRP	CASI2
	Climate refugees, relocation	Airborne and sub-orbital: OMG, S-MODE, AirSWOT, SWOT cal/val, Delta-X	World Bank	Future: Climate & Resilience Applications teams/projects
Threat to ecosystems and biodiversity	Emergency preparedness	Modeling: ECCO, GISS-E, GMAO, regional DA & Digital Twins	National sealevel.gov	
	Insurance & Finances	Computational and integration infrastructure: IPCC, EIS, SLPS	Federal, state, and global practitioners	
	NASA centers and launch services	Public face and climate tools: sealevel.nasa.gov	Climate assessments	
			NASA EIC	

4. PPBE FY25, Future Needs and Opportunities

NASA's foundational and unparalleled sea level research efforts are well coordinated and mature, providing an excellent springboard for further applications. From this foundation, we are already addressing the common needs of a broad range of stakeholders. This will increase NASA's visibility and engagement, which can then be followed by opportunities for more targeted technical efforts. Maintaining and advancing these contributions are a service to the American public and global community. NASA's continued investments in connecting this work with a user community has brought NASA's contribution from useful science to usable science, and has made strong inroads into science that is being used by stakeholders. To continue NASA's leading role in the sea level enterprise and to enhance our work on the science to application spectrum, the following needs can be met with additional resources and opportunities:

4.1 Enhance research-to-action, collaboration, and transition of useful science to science that is being used:

- Elevate NASA's role in the U.S. Federal domain, e.g. take leading role in sealevel.gov, USGCRP, and WH SOST efforts.
- Expand use-case applications that highlight adaptation pathways to increase community resilience to sea level change.
- Expand work with boundary organizations to enable scaling of N-SLCT efforts, e.g. through expansion of existing networks that can help both disseminate and inform NASA efforts.
- Increase usability and compatibility of existing climate and sea level tools across the agency and federal partners to enable further uses of sea level information with socio-economic data(e.g., population, income, infrastructure, etc.)
- Enhance cross-ESD collaboration and partnering (e.g., R&A and Applied programs)

4.2 Advance sea level science to inform future solutions:

- Improve robustness of sea level projections and coastal impacts with new types of measurement system (e.g., active air-sea observing to improve predictability of extremes)
- Expand workforce, both engineering and scientific
- Maintain our existing climate web-based tools that feed into multiple national and global efforts
- Have mission continuity to ensure delivery of relevant and high-quality content
- Establish cloud-cost funds and provide AWS credits for scientists do their job.

5. References

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